

Deciphering a New Electrolyte Formulation for Intelligent Modulation of Thermal Runaway to Improve the Safety of Lithium-Ion Batteries

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Thermal runaway remains a persisting challenge that poses a significant risk to lithium-ion battery (LIB) users. In commercial LIBs, thermal runaway is typically controlled using temperature-responsive trilayer polypropylene/polyethylene/polypropylene (PP/PE/PP) separators. However, because of thermal shrinkage at ≈ 160 °C, these separators often fail to prevent thermal runaway in practical LIBs. Electrolyte engineering is, therefore, crucial to mitigate the risk of thermal runaway in LIBs. In this context, the Diels-Alder click chemistry is being introduced to tackle the thermal runaway issues in LIBs. A thermoresponsive electrolyte is proposed composed of a lithium salt dissolved in vinylene carbonate (VC) and 2,5-dimethylfuran (DMFu) that functions effectively in batteries at room temperature. At high temperatures, VC and DMFu participate in Diels-Alder reactions, forming oligomers that significantly decrease the ionic conductivity of the electrolyte and concurrently occlude the micropores of PP/PE/PP separators. These dual effects enable a two-step intelligent modulation of thermal runaway, with a warning phase activated above 80 °C and a complete thermal shutdown at 120 °C. The thermoresponsive electrolyte formulation deciphered in this study holds great potential for advancing the safety of LIBs through electrolyte engineering.

the transportation sector to grid-scale energy storage technologies supporting and strengthening the power grid to facilitate greater intermittency. However, the pace of renewable energy storage and transition greatly relies on the safety of LIBs.^[2] Despite significant advancements in energy density, power density, and cycle life of LIBs, safety threats to these batteries caused by thermal runaway persist.^[3] The LIBs inevitably undergo catastrophic exothermic chemical reactions, including thermal decomposition of the solid electrolyte interphase, the reaction of intercalated lithium in graphite anode with organic solvents in the electrolyte, thermal breakdown of the cathode, etc.^[4] These exothermic reactions release considerable heat that triggers the thermal runaway event where the internal temperature of the batteries gradually rises.^[5,6] When the temperature inside batteries reaches a critical value, the internal temperature and pressure of the batteries escalate rapidly, potentially leading to explosion and fire.^[7,8] Commercial LIBs have external pressure-release vents and positive temperature coefficient resistors to control overpressure and overheating. However, the increase in pressure and temperature within the cells occurs more rapidly before these external devices can detect

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have dominated the consumer market of electronic equipment and electric vehicles in the past few decades.^[1] The practical applications of LIBs vary widely from

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them.^[9] Therefore, internal safety mechanisms are more effective in preventing thermal runaway.

There have been considerable efforts to design internal functional components to address battery safety issues. Trilayer polypropylene/polyethylene/polypropylene (PP/PE/PP) separators with intrinsic thermal shutdown mechanisms, commercialized by Celgard, are the most sought-after internal functional component that safeguards LIBs from thermal runaway.^[10] When the internal temperature of LIBs reaches a critical temperature (≈ 135 °C), the porous PE layer softens and partially melts and closes the film micropores. Consequently, the conduction of Li^+ ions between the electrodes is prevented, permanently terminating the battery operation. The external two PP layers maintain the mechanical integrity of the separator. However, these PP/PE/PP trilayer separators often fail to prevent thermal runaway in practical applications. This is because the melting point of PE (130 °C) is only 30 °C lower than the melting temperature of PP (160 °C). Thermal inertia after battery shutdown can easily cause the internal temperature of the batteries to reach the melting point of PP, leading to the separator shrinking and causing an internal short-circuit.^[11,12] In certain instances, cells with thermal shutdown separators remain inactive for as little as three minutes before failing due to internal short circuits.^[11] Although ceramic coating layers significantly improve the mechanical strength and thermal stability of battery separators, the polyolefin membrane is still susceptible to shrinking after thermal shutdown because of thermal inertia.^[13–15] Therewithal, the ceramic coating layer may easily delaminate from the separator during battery manufacturing and use.^[16] White et al.^[17] described an innovative concept of coating the anode or separator with certain polyethylene microspheres that create an ion-insulating barrier upon melting at 110 °C, which prevents further battery operation. Ai et al.^[18] introduced a temperature-responsive separator by casting a slurry of ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) microspheres onto the commercial PP/PE/PP trilayer separator. When EVA microspheres melt at 90 °C, they coalesce together to occlude the micropores of the separator, halting Li^+ ion conduction between the electrodes and consequently shutting down the LIBs. Wang et al.^[19] reported a polyamine (PA) layer-coated polyethylene separator with controllable pores to enhance safety. Although incorporating such thermoresponsive material-coated separators enhances the safety of LIBs, their practical utilization is limited by the complexity of preparation processes and the vulnerability of the coating layers to detach from the separators during cell assembly or battery operation.^[20] Additional effective strategies for LIB thermal management include water-tolerant solid polymer electrolytes, heat-storage ionomer binders, and cationic covalent organic frameworks with ultralow HOMO energy.^[21–23]

Temperature-responsive electrolytes including lower critical solution temperature electrolytes provide a promising alternative to mitigate thermal runaway in LIBs.^[24–32] These electrolytes are designed to cease Li^+ ion transport spontaneously when a specific temperature threshold is exceeded, restraining internal temperature accrual and reducing the risk of catastrophic battery failure. Three key temperatures define the temperature rise in LIBs during thermal runaway: T_1 , where the anode contributes to self-heating; T_2 , where reactions between the anode and electrolyte lead to thermal runaway; and T_3 , the maximum temperature caused by exothermic reactions with the elec-

trodes and electrolyte. Once thermal runaway reaches T_2 , LIBs quickly reach catastrophic temperatures, overwhelming safety measures. The SEI decomposition happens before T_1 , so stopping the temperature rise at or before T_1 is critical for developing intrinsically safe LIBs, ensuring thermal reversibility in their performance. Therefore, it is both necessary and challenging to conceptually design thermoresponsive electrolytes that facilitate a gradual decline in electrochemical performance (acting as a warning phase) before the thermal shutdown of the batteries. However, none of the afore-referenced temperature-responsive electrolytes (such as polymeric gel electrolytes) or the modified separators or ionomer binders are capable of fulfilling this requirement.

Since the discovery of the Diels-Alder cycloaddition reaction in 1928, it has become one of the most significant organic reactions, playing a crucial role in designing complex organic molecules into polymers.^[33–36] In this study, we developed a liquid electrolyte composed of two organic solvents, vinylene carbonate (VC) and 2,5-dimethylfuran (DMFu), which are envisioned to participate in thermally induced Diels-Alder reactions^[37] to discontinue the battery operation at elevated temperatures. Diels-Alder reactions were previously introduced in lithium-ion batteries to create self-healing polymer electrolyte membranes^[38] and electrode binders.^[39,40] However, this report proposes using Diels-Alder click chemistry to address thermal runaway in lithium-ion batteries for the first time. The electrolyte possesses a prerequisite ionic conductivity of 1.18×10^{-3} S cm^{-1} at room temperature and functions effectively in batteries. Importantly, the Li^+ ion conduction between the electrodes substantially diminishes at elevated temperatures due to Diels-Alder reactions between VC and DMFu, offering a two-stage intelligent modulation of thermal runaway — a warning mode above 80 °C and a complete thermal shutdown at 120 °C. The warning mode would assist in adjusting electrochemical performance at the onset of SEI decomposition,^[41] providing additional time to manage thermal runaway. Moreover, the dimensional stability of the separator is maintained after thermal shutdown at 120 °C, further protecting the batteries from the risk of thermal runaway. The cessation of battery operation at 120 °C is due to a significant increase in charge transfer resistance, resulting from the macromolecules (oligomers) produced through Diels-Alder reactions. These oligomers reduce Li^+ ion conductivity and obstruct the micropores of the battery separator, significantly reducing ionic conduction between the electrodes and eventually leading to battery shutdown.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Design Principle of Thermoresponsive Electrolytes

A typical LIB comprises a flammable organic electrolyte and two electrodes, separated by a porous polyolefin separator with a melting point of ~ 160 °C. This type of battery usually operates at a high cell voltage that surpasses the thermodynamic stability threshold. When excessive heat is produced due to short-circuiting or overcharging, the separator melts, initiating and accelerating exothermic reactions between the electrodes and the electrolyte. Such incidents exacerbate the catastrophic thermal runaway, causing explosion and fire. Our proof of concept to

Scheme 1. Illustration of safe battery design: Safe LIBs incorporate a thermoresponsive electrolyte operating normally at room temperature. However, the electrolyte solvents undergo Diels-Alder reactions at elevated temperatures, producing different oligomers. These oligomers block the micropores of the polyolefin separator, leading to a significant decrease in Li^+ ion conduction and thermal shutdown of the battery.

enhance the safety of LIB by incorporating a thermoresponsive liquid electrolyte is demonstrated in **Scheme 1**. We introduce a liquid electrolyte composed of two organic solvents, vinylene carbonate (VC) and 2,5-dimethylfuran (DMFu), which undergo a thermally induced Diels-Alder reaction at a high temperature.^[37] The Diels-Alder reaction between VC (dienophile) and DMFu (diene) produces oligomers that significantly lower Li^+ ion conduction between the electrodes. Such a phenomenon leads to the thermal shutdown of LIBs at a high temperature, though still considerably lower than the thermal shrinkage temperature of the polyolefin separators. As a result, the polyolefin separators maintain their dimensional stability after the thermal shutdown, preventing battery explosion.

To achieve high Li^+ ion conductivity in a liquid electrolyte, it is essential to dissolve a substantial amount of lithium salt. At the same time, to improve LIB safety through the thermal shutdown, it is envisioned that the electrolyte solvents should undergo temperature-induced Diels-Alder cycloaddition reactions that ensure complete immobilization of Li^+ ions at an elevated temperature. The extent of Diels-Alder reactions primarily re-

lies on the relative abundance of diene molecules. However, a trade-off between the quantities of lithium salt and DMFu (diene) was noticed while preparing our thermoresponsive electrolytes. Simultaneous increase in Li-salt and DMFu leads to a phase separation in the solution, likely due to the low dielectric constant of DMFu. However, combining LiTFSI with a mixture of DMFu and VC in an optimized molar ratio of 0.15:0.8:1.0 results in a homogeneous solution that ensures the highest respective molar amounts of lithium salt and diene. This solution is designated and further referred to as $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte.

2.2. Electrochemical Performances

The oxidative stability of the $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte was evaluated in Li||Al and Li||SS cell configurations. Linear sweep voltammetry study reveals the oxidative stability of the thermoresponsive electrolyte up to 3.92 V versus Li^+/Li (**Figure 1a**), and therefore, could be suitable against the LiFePO_4

Figure 1. Measurements of electrochemical properties of thermoresponsive electrolyte: a) Evaluation of oxidative stability of the electrolyte measured by LSV starting from OCV to high potential on SS and Al current collectors; b) estimation of ionic conductivity by EIS technique; c) Li^+ ion transference number measurement by chronoamperometry and EIS techniques; d) EIS spectra of a symmetrical Li cell during the rest period.

cathode. The ionic conductivity (σ) of the electrolyte was determined using the EIS technique. The corresponding Nyquist plot is shown in Figure 1b. The $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte shows a high ionic conductivity of 1.18 mS cm^{-1} at room temperature. Li||Li symmetric cells were employed to measure the transference number of the electrolyte. The lithium-ion transference number of the $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte is estimated to be higher than ($t_{\text{Li}^+} = 0.58$) the conventional LP30 electrolyte ($t_{\text{Li}^+} = 0.46$),^[42] as represented in Figure 1c. We attribute the relatively high lithium-ion transference number of the electrolyte to the larger size of the TFSI⁻ anion. A high ion transference in the electrolyte can reduce concentration polarization during battery cycling, enhancing the rate capability and preventing lithium dendrite formation.^[43] The SEI stability was assessed by monitoring the interfacial impedance of Li||Li symmetric cells during a rest period. The interfacial impedance of Li||Li symmetric cells using a reference DMFu-based electrolyte (0.3 M LiTFSI solution in DMFu) steadily and remarkably increased with rest time (Figure S1, Supporting Information), suggesting the development of an unstable passivation layer on the Li electrodes. Such an unstable passivation layer fails to stop the ongoing parasitic reactions between the electrolyte and the Li electrode, resulting in the continuous growth of the passivation layer. A steady increase in the interfacial impedance up to 48 h of rest time was also observed for a symmetrical Li cell with $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte, indicating the formation of an interfacial layer over the Li electrode surface. However, the change in interfacial impedance was negligible from 48 to 72 h, manifesting excellent stability of

the as-formed interfacial layer between the Li electrode and the electrolyte (Figure 1d).

To assess the long-term electrochemical stability of the $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte with Li electrodes, Li||Li symmetrical cells were cycled at different current densities with 1-h polarization in each direction. The Li plating/stripping behavior of a Li symmetric cell at the current density of 0.5 mA cm^{-2} with a total capacity of 0.5 mA h cm^{-2} is represented in Figure 2a. The lithium plating and stripping overpotential of the symmetric cell gradually decreased after the initial few cycles (Figure S2, Supporting Information), which indicates a stable passivation layer forming over the Li electrode surface.^[44,45] The cell subsequently demonstrated stable Li plating and stripping behavior for over 2000 h (or 1000 cycles). The Li symmetric cells with the $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte also exhibited stable long-term Li plating/stripping cycling at a higher current density of 1 mA cm^{-2} with a total capacity of 1 mA h cm^{-2} (Figure 2b; Figure S3, Supporting Information). The impedance analysis of the cells shows an initial decrease in interfacial resistance, followed by stabilization, further corroborating the formation of a stable and Li^+ ion-conductive interface (Figure S4, Supporting Information). The SEM images of cycled Li electrodes show the compact aggregates of large nodule-like morphologies of electrodeposited lithium^[46] with no obvious filament-like lithium dendrites (Figure 2c,d; Figure S5, Supporting Information). Such low-surface-area, nodule-like lithium morphology can greatly mitigate the continuous side reactions with electrolyte solvents, thus endowing high Coulombic efficiency and

Figure 2. Li plating and stripping experiments and morphology characterization: a) Li plating/stripping experiment at 0.5 mA cm^{-2} current density and 0.5 mA h cm^{-2} capacity; b) Li plating/stripping experiment at 1.0 mA cm^{-2} current density and 1 mA h cm^{-2} capacity; c) SEM image of Li electrode after 100 cycles of Li plating/stripping at 0.5 mA cm^{-2} current density and 0.5 mA h cm^{-2} capacity; d) SEM image of Li electrode after 100 cycles of Li plating/stripping at 1 mA cm^{-2} current density and 1 mA h cm^{-2} capacity.

improved cycle life in lithium metal batteries.^[47] The XPS analysis of the cycled Li electrode surface reveals an SEI layer composed of poly(vinylene carbonate) and lithium alkyl carbonate (Figure S6, Supporting Information). It is known that the highly reactive VC polymerizes (reduces) during battery cycling, promoting the formation of poly(vinylene carbonate)-rich SEI film that improves cell performance by inhibiting the continuous reduction of electrolytes on the anode surface and suppressing lithium dendrite formation.^[48–50] To further investigate the robustness of the poly(vinylene carbonate)-rich SEI layer during Li plating/stripping cycling, we examined the rate capability of a Li symmetrical cell at various current densities with 1-h polarization in each direction. The Li symmetrical cell displayed stable Li plating and stripping performance at a high current density of up to 2 mA cm^{-2} (Figure S7, Supporting Information). During the variable current rate performance of the Li symmetrical cell, no dendrite formation (soft short circuits) or significant increase in overpotential was detected.

The electrochemical properties of the $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte were further evaluated in lithium metal batteries containing commercial LiFePO_4 cathode with high areal capacity (2.0 mA h cm^{-2}). Figure 3a represents the galvanostatic charge-

discharge profiles of a $\text{Li}||\text{LiFePO}_4$ cell at a current rate of 0.1 C ($1\text{C} = \text{theoretical capacity of LFP} = 170 \text{ mA g}^{-1}$) within the potential range of 3.55 to 3 V (vs Li^+/Li). The cell exhibited a charge plateau at 3.4 V, corresponding to the de-intercalation of Li^+ ions from the LiFePO_4 crystal, and a discharge plateau at 3.45 V, signifying the insertion of Li^+ ions back into the LiFePO_4 crystal.^[51] The cell delivered a specific capacity of $169.2 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$ during the initial charging and $163.7 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$ during the following discharging. The excess specific capacity observed during the initial charge may be attributed to the irreversible consumption of Li^+ ions due to VC reduction, forming an SEI film on the Li anode. Given that VC has an oxidation potential greater than 4.3 V versus Li^+/Li ,^[52] the likelihood of a passivation layer generating on the LiFePO_4 cathode surface due to VC oxidation is minimal. However, the charge-discharge voltage hysteresis of the $\text{Li}||\text{LiFePO}_4$ cell gradually decreased as cycling progressed (Figure S8, Supporting Information). This could be attributed to the regressive interfacial charge transfer resistance of the $\text{Li}||\text{LiFePO}_4$ cell during cycling, as indicated by EIS analysis (Figure S9, Supporting Information). The galvanostatic charge-discharge profiles of the $\text{Li}||\text{LiFePO}_4$ cells at various current rates are shown in Figure 3b. The voltage hysteresis was found to increase with increasing

Figure 3. Performance of LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte in Li||LiFePO₄ coin cells: a) charge-discharge profiles at 0.1C current density; b) charge-discharge profiles at various current densities; c) charge-discharge cycling performance at 0.1C current density; d) rate performance at various current densities.

current rates, which could be ascribed to the diffusion-limited charge transfer kinetics in the LiFePO₄ cathode.^[53,54] The Li||LiFePO₄ cell delivered an initial reversible capacity of 163.9 mA h g⁻¹ during 2nd cycle, retaining 129.2 mA h g⁻¹ after 200 cycles with an average Coulombic efficiency of 99.7% at 0.1C current density (Figure 3c). This result manifests that the electrolyte was competently stable in the Li||LiFePO₄ cells. The rate performance of the Li||LiFePO₄ cell is represented in Figure 3d. The cell delivered average specific capacities of 164.3, 145.2, 127.8, and 114.2 mA h g⁻¹ at the different current densities of 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, and 1C, respectively. Notably, the cell exhibited nearly identical specific capacity when the current rate was reversed to 0.1C.

The electrochemical performance of the LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte was further explored in graphite||LiFePO₄ full cells with commercial LiFePO₄ cathode and graphite anode with high areal capacities of 2.0 and 2.4 mA h cm⁻², respectively. The graphite||LiFePO₄ cells displayed distinct multistep charge-discharge plateaus (Figure 4a), associated with the multi-stage

lithiation of the graphite anode.^[55] The cell achieved a specific capacity of 165.4 mA h g⁻¹ during the initial charging and 158.1 mA h g⁻¹ during subsequent discharging. As with the Li||LiFePO₄ cell, charge-discharge voltage hysteresis of the graphite||LiFePO₄ cell gradually reduces with cycling (Figure 4b). The corresponding charge-discharge cycling performance of the graphite||LiFePO₄ cell at 0.1C current density is shown in Figure 4c. The cell delivered an initial reversible specific capacity of 157.8 mA h g⁻¹ during 2nd cycle, retaining 76% and 62% of the initial capacity after 200 and 300 cycles, respectively. The long-term cyclability of the LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte in graphite||LiFePO₄ full cells is attributable to the thin and homogeneous SEI layer generated on the surface of the graphite anode (Figure S10, Supporting Information).

To validate the potential of the LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte in practical LIBs, a single-layer pouch cell was fabricated using the commercial LiFePO₄ cathode and the graphite anode. Figure 5a,b schematically illustrates a configuration of the pouch cell and its working mechanism. During operation, consistent

Figure 4. Electrochemical performance of LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte in graphite||LiFePO₄ coin cells: a) charge-discharge profiles at 0.1C; b) enlarged charge-discharge profiles at 0.1C; c) charge-discharge cycling performance at 0.1C.

Figure 5. Electrochemical performance of the graphite||LiFePO₄ pouch cell: a,b) Configuration and working mechanism of pouch cell; c) charge/discharge profiles at a current density of 0.1C (0.19 mA cm⁻²) for different cycles; d) corresponding cycling performance of pouch cell at a current density of 0.1C (0.19 mA cm⁻²).

Figure 6. Characterization of Diels-Alder reaction in $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte: a) solid-state ^1H NMR spectrum of the electrolyte after heat treatment at $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; b) MALDI-TOF MS spectrum of the electrolyte after heat treatment at $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; c) plausible chemical structure of an oligomer formed by Diels-Alder reactions.

pressure was applied to the pouch cell to reduce the contact resistance between the electrodes and the separator (Figure S11, Supporting Information). The charge-discharge profiles of the pouch cells for different cycles reveal nearly identical voltage polarization during cycling (Figure 5c). The pouch cell exhibits an initial areal charge capacity of 1.27 and 1.15 mA h cm^{-2} during the following discharge, retaining 0.87 mA h cm^{-2} after 30 cycles (Figure 5d). It should be noted that there is a wide performance gap between the coin and pouch cells. The quantity of the electrolyte inevitably exists in excess in the coin cells, leading to distinctly better performance than that of the pouch cells.

2.3. Characterization of Diels-Alder Reactions

Solid-state ^1H NMR and mass spectroscopy were employed to characterize Diels-Alder reactions in the $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte. A noticeable change in the color of the electrolyte after heat treatment seemingly suggests an alteration in its physicochemical properties (Figure S12, Supporting Information). The ^1H NMR spectrum of the pristine electrolyte exhibits the characteristic ^1H NMR peaks of VC (7.65 ppm) and DMFu (2.2 and 5.9 ppm) (Figure S13, Supporting Information). However, the characteristic ^1H NMR peaks of DMFu disappeared in the heat-treated electrolyte, indicating nearly all DMFu (diene) molecules participated in Diels-Alder reactions with VC (Figure 6a). The emergence of a new peak at the chemical shift of 4.8 ppm (des-

ignated as H_γ) is analogous to the proton bonded to the methyl-substituted carbon in cyclic propylene carbonate,^[56,57] and therefore, we attribute this finding to the participation of VC as a dienophile to the Diels-Alder reactions.^[37] Moreover, the new ^1H NMR peak at the chemical shift of 6.1 ppm is ascribed to the protons (designated as H_α) connected to the C=C double bond of the terminal oxygen-bridged norbornene unit in each VC-(DMFu)_n oligomer produced by a series of Diels-Alder reactions. The peak at 1.4 ppm can be assigned to the protons of methyl groups attached to oxygen-bridged norbornane units in VC-(DMFu)_n oligomers. Interestingly, no characteristic ^1H NMR peaks for poly(vinylene carbonate) were detected in the chemical shift range of 5.4–5.7 ppm.^[58,59] The average molecular weight of the VC-(DMFu)_n oligomers was analyzed through the MALDI-TOF mass spectroscopy characterization technique. The MALDI-TOF MS spectrum of the heat-treated electrolyte displayed an oligomer molecular ion peak $\approx 1356.8\text{ m z}^{-1}$ (Figure 6b), attributed to the $[\text{VC}-(\text{DMFu})_{13} + \text{Na}]^+$ species. A chemical structure of a representative oligomer analogous to the empirical formula of VC-(DMFu)₁₃ is shown in Figure 6c. GPC analysis of the heat-treated electrolyte revealed a notable shift toward lower retention time (Figure S14, Supporting Information), further suggesting the oligomerization reaction between VC and DMFu. The DOSY NMR spectrum of electrolytes at $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ reveals a 1.8-fold decrease in the diffusion coefficient from $6.4 \times 10^{-10}\text{ m}^2\text{ s}^{-1}$ to $3.5 \times 10^{-10}\text{ m}^2\text{ s}^{-1}$ (Figure S15, Supporting Information), corroborating the formation of higher molecular weight species.

Figure 7. Electrochemical performance of graphite||LiFePO₄ full cells with different electrolytes at various temperatures: a) charge-discharge profiles of the cells with LP30 and LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolytes across various temperatures at 0.1C, b) voltage profiles of cells with LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte at 0.1C, c) cycle number versus capacity plot of the cell with LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte at 0.1C, d) temperature-dependent internal resistance of a stainless steel symmetric cell with LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte.

To investigate the influence of oligomer formation on the relative solubility of the lithium salt in the LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte, temperature-dependent solid-state ⁷Li NMR studies were conducted (Figure S16, Supporting Information). At 25 °C, the ⁷Li NMR spectrum shows a sharp peak, indicating the lithium salt is fully dissolved and the electrolyte is homogeneous, resulting in a uniform electronic environment around the ⁷Li nuclei. However, as the temperature increases, the NMR peak gradually broadens and the peak area decreases. This change is attributed to alterations in the electronic environment of the ⁷Li nuclei (likely due to the formation of oligomers of varying molecular weights), reduced lithium salt solubility (perhaps due to conformational constraints in the oligomers), and increased sample viscosity.

2.4. Evaluation of Thermal Shutdown Behavior of the Electrolytes

The thermal shutdown behavior of the LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte was assessed and compared with that of the conventional carbonate-based LP30 electrolyte using Swagelok cells. The graphite||LiFePO₄ full-cell configuration was adopted to avoid the possibility of parasitic reactions of the electrolyte with the Li anode at high temperatures.^[59] The cells with respective electrolytes were first cycled at the current rate of 0.1C at

room temperature (25 °C) to verify the cell operation. The cells were subsequently cycled at 80 and 120 °C, respectively. Both graphite||LiFePO₄ cells exhibited characteristic multistep charge-discharge plateaus at 25 and 80 °C (Figure 7a). The cell containing the LP30 electrolyte continued to function even at 120 °C, as indicated by the charge profile. It should be mentioned that commercial LIBs with a trilayer separator and the traditional carbonate-based electrolyte (e.g., LP30 electrolyte) exhibit thermal shutdown behavior at an elevated temperature close to 135 °C.^[17] However, this trilayer separator often malfunctions to prevent thermal runaway in LIBs. The small difference in melting points between PE and PP allows thermal inertia after battery shutdown to easily cause the separator to collapse, ultimately leading to an internal short-circuit. The graphite||LiFePO₄ cell with the LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte achieved a reversible specific capacity of 152 mA h g⁻¹ when cycled at a 0.1C rate at room temperature (Figure 7b,c). At 80 °C, the specific capacity slightly increased to 158 mA h g⁻¹, benefiting from improved charge transport kinetics at elevated temperatures.^[60] However, the specific capacity dropped significantly to 45 mA h g⁻¹ at 100 °C, signaling a gradual suppression of electrochemical activity as an early warning mechanism (Figure 7b,c). The cell exhibited a strict thermal shutdown behavior when the temperature was further raised to 120 °C. These findings divulge that the thermoresponsive LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte enables a

two-step intelligent modulation of thermal runaway in LIBs, with a warning phase at $\geq 100^\circ\text{C}$ and a complete thermal shutdown at a temperature notably lower than the thermal shrinkage temperature of commercial trilayer separators. As a result, the separator retains its mechanical integrity after the thermal shutdown, helping to prevent battery combustion and explosion.

The thermal shutdown behavior of the $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte was analyzed using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements. The EIS spectra of a stainless steel symmetric cell incorporating a Celgard 2325 separator soaked with the electrolyte, measured at temperatures of 25, 60, and 80°C , reveal nearly similar electrolyte resistance, R_s , and the lack of a semicircle in the spectra indicate the absence of interfacial charge transfer resistance, R_{ct} (Figure S17, Supporting Information). However, the EIS spectra of the same symmetrical cell exhibited semicircles (corresponding to R_{ct}) at 100 and 120°C . The R_s values increased to 8.4 and $182.7\ \Omega$, respectively, at 100 and 120°C . As a result, the $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte exhibited an ionic conductivity of 1.37×10^{-5} at 120°C (Figure S18, Supporting Information). The substantial decrease in ionic conductivity of the $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte by two orders of magnitude can be ascribed to the increased sample viscosity and reduced lithium salt solubility. The R_{ct} values of the symmetric cell were estimated to be $132\ \Omega$ at 100°C and $3946\ \Omega$ at 120°C . The significantly high charge transfer resistance at 120°C is attributed to the evolution of an ion-insulating interlayer, exclusively resulting from the Diels-Alder reactions. Therefore, the thermal shutdown behavior of the thermoresponsive $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte is attributed to a substantial increase in total internal resistance ($R_s + R_{ct}$), as illustrated in Figure 7d. The thermal shutdown feature of the $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolyte was further assessed in the graphite|| LiFePO_4 pouch cell. An additional charge-discharge test on the pouch cell was conducted after 30 cycles at room temperature, followed by a heat treatment at 120°C for 1.5 h (including the time required to attend to a thermal equilibrium inside the cell). The pouch cell exhibited abrupt voltage changes without any capacity contribution during charging and discharging (Figure S19, Supporting Information), attributed to the significant overpotential resulting from the restricted conduction of Li^+ ions between the electrodes. We believe that variations in electrolyte viscosity play a pivotal role in triggering the warning phase and thermal shutdown behavior. To investigate this, rheological studies were conducted to determine the time required for changes in the complex viscosity of the electrolyte system at 100 and 120°C . The complex viscosity of the electrolyte was measured isothermally at these temperatures to evaluate viscosity changes associated with Diels-Alder reactions. At 120°C , the electrolyte viscosity surged sharply (4.2×10^3 mPa·s in 10 min), indicating rapid Diels-Alder reactions and plateaued at 7.2×10^7 mPa·s after 230 min due to increased molecular weight (inset, Figure S20, Supporting Information). In contrast, at 100°C , the viscosity increased gradually (2.7×10^3 mPa·s in 10 min), initiating a warning phase (inset, Figure S20, Supporting Information). The four-order magnitude rise in viscosity at 120°C caused a complete thermal shutdown of the battery.

Moreover, the origin of the thermal shutdown behavior of the pouch cell can be envisaged by analyzing the optical images and SEM morphologies of a pristine separator and the separator retrieved from the pouch cell after the thermal shutdown. The color of the separator retrieved from the pouch cell after the thermal shutdown was noticed to be changed to brown, in contrast to the characteristic color of the pristine separator (Figure 8a,b; Figure S21, Supporting Information). The SEM image of the pristine separator exhibits abundant micropores that provide sufficient channels for liquid electrolytes to pass through (Figure 8c). In contrast, the SEM image obtained from the brown area of the separator retrieved from the pouch cell after thermal shutdown displays a uniform coating of Diels-Alder products (i.e., oligomers) on the surface of the separator (Figure 8d). It is important to note that the separator retained its dimensional stability and the characteristic micropores at 120°C , as evidenced by the SEM image acquired from the edge of the identical separator (Figure 8e). As obvious, the pristine separator also maintains its characteristic pores and dimensional stability even at elevated temperatures (Figure S22, Supporting Information). Furthermore, the cross-sectional SEM images display a clear distinction between the electrolyte-soaked separators before and after heat treatment (Figure S23, Supporting Information). After exposure to heat, the formation of oligomers and their accumulation within the micropores of the separator become apparent, effectively obstructing the Li^+ ion transport channels. This observation supports the thermoresponsive shutdown mechanism of the electrolyte.

To evaluate the safety limits of the Diels-Alder oligomers-modified separator recovered from the pouch cell after thermal shutdown, its thermal shrinkage properties were analyzed at various elevated temperatures and compared with those of the pristine separator. As shown in Figure S24 (Supporting Information), the significant thermal shrinkage of the pristine separator at 150°C is attributed to the melting of the inner PE layer (melting point of PE = 135°C). The anisotropic dimensional shrinkage of the pristine separator can be ascribed to the manufacturing process, in which the separator is stretched in the machine direction.^[10] Upon heating at 170°C for 0.5 h, the pristine separator became transparent due to the melting of the PE and PP layers. In contrast, the Diels-Alder oligomers-modified separator exhibited minimal shrinkage under heat treatment at 150°C and 170°C . Moreover, to investigate the effect of Diels-Alder oligomers on the thermal stability of the PP/PE/PP separators and safety thresholds of the LIBs at elevated temperatures, the open circuit potentials of fully charged graphite|| LiFePO_4 Swagelok cells incorporating respective LP30 and $\text{LiTFSI}_{0.15}\text{DMFu}_{0.8}\text{VC}_{1.0}$ electrolytes were monitored at 150°C and 170°C . The cells were charged at room temperature, heat-treated at 120°C for 1.5 h, and then transferred to an oven at 150°C or 170°C . For cells with pristine separators, the OCP dropped to 0 V within 40 min at 150°C and within 25 min at 170°C , likely due to thermal shrinkage of the separator, causing an internal short circuit (Figure 8f,g). In contrast, cells with oligomers-modified separators maintained their OCP for over 70 min at both temperatures (Figure 8f,g), demonstrating that these separators preserved dimensional stability under high temperatures.

Figure 8. Characterization of Celgard separator retrieved from the pouch cell after thermal shutdown: a,b) digital images of pristine separator and the separator retrieved from the pouch cell after thermal shutdown (scale bar = 1 cm), c) SEM image of pristine separator (scale bar = 500 nm), d,e) SEM images acquired from the brown area and the edge of the separator retrieved from the pouch cell after thermal shutdown (scale bar = 500 nm), f,g) changes in the open-circuit potentials of fully charged graphite||LiFePO₄ cells containing pristine and Diels-Alder oligomer-modified PP/PE/PP separators at 150 °C and 170 °C.

3. Conclusion

Designing thermoresponsive electrolytes that facilitate a gradual reduction in electrochemical performance while precisely aligning with the critical temperatures responsible for thermal runaways is highly desired, yet challenging. This work introduces a conceptually new thermoresponsive liquid electrolyte composed of VC and DMFu solvents, which demonstrates an ionic conductivity of $1.18 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ and a high lithium-ion transference number (t_{Li^+}) of 0.58 at room temperature. The electrolyte promotes stable lithium plating and stripping in Li symmetric cells while ensuring long-term cycling stability in both Li||LiFePO₄ and graphite||LiFePO₄ batteries by forming a robust poly(vinylene carbonate)-rich SEI layer on the anode surface. Single-layer graphite||LiFePO₄ pouch cell incorporating this electrolyte delivered an initial areal capacity of 1.15 mAh cm^{-2} and retained 0.87 mAh cm^{-2} after 30 cycles at a current density of 0.1C (0.19 mA cm^{-2}). At elevated temperatures, the VC and DMFu undergo Diels-Alder reactions, producing macromolecules that significantly reduce the Li⁺ ion conductivity of the electrolyte and concurrently obstruct the micropores of the separator. These dual effects allow for a two-step smart regulation of thermal runaway, initiating a warning phase at 100 °C and achieving a complete thermal shutdown at 120 °C. Furthermore, the Diels-Alder oligomers-modified PP/PE/PP separator demonstrates im-

proved thermal stability with minimal shrinkage, thereby significantly increasing the safety limits of the batteries. Our comprehensive understanding of the effective endowment of the Diels-Alder reaction for thermal runaway protection of LIBs paves the way for designing new electrolytes with thermal shutdown capabilities.

4. Experimental Section

Electrolyte Preparation: The thermoresponsive electrolyte was prepared in an argon-filled glove box by dissolving lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI, Sigma Aldrich) into a mixture of 2,5-dimethylfuran (DMFu, Sigma Aldrich) and vinylene carbonate (VC, Sigma Aldrich) at an optimized molar ratio of 0.15:0.8:1.0. The solution was continuously stirred until a uniform solution was obtained. The resulting light brown solution was referred to as LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte.

Physical Characterization: The molecular weight of the oligomers was determined using a matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometer (MALDI-TOF MS, Bruker autoflex Max) using tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0) (TTP, 99%, Sigma Aldrich) as a matrix. Solid-state ¹H and ⁷Li NMR spectra were obtained with a Bruker AVANCE III HD 400 WB spectrometer. The XPS analysis was carried out using a PHI 5700 X-ray photoelectron spectrometer. The relative molecular weight distributions of the starting materials (VC, and DMFu) and the thermoresponsive electrolyte were determined using the gel permeation chromatography (GPC) OmniSec, Malvern CHR6110 (Resolve and Reveal)

fitted with a Viscotek VE3580 refractive index and viscosity detectors. A set of two Viscotek T6000 M, general mixed organic (300 × 8 mm) columns were used. The detector and the column temperature were held constant at 35 °C and the samples solution (5 mg mL⁻¹ in THF) was eluted at 1 mL min⁻¹ flow rate using THF (>99.9%, HPLC grade, inhibitor-free). GPC data was analyzed using OmniSec (v 11.20) software. The structure of the synthesized compounds was verified by proton, and diffusion-ordered (DOSY) nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) experiments on a Bruker AV400 NMR, 400 MHz, FT-NMR spectrometer. The chemical shifts were reported as δ values (ppm) using DMSO-d₆ or mesitylene (internal standard) as reference solvents. The data was processed and analyzed using the MestReNova (14.2.1) software. An MCR302e rheometer (Anton Paar) equipped with a parallel plate geometry and a convection temperature device (CTD-600) was used to monitor the time-dependent changes in the complex viscosity of the electrolyte. The sample was promptly placed on a disposable 25 mm lower measuring plate and sandwiched with a 25 mm upper plate. The mixture was then heated isothermally at either 100 or 120 °C for 4 h. SEM images were captured with a Thermo Fisher Scientific Apreo 2S LoVac field-emission scanning electron microscope.

Electrochemical Measurements: Electrochemical measurements were carried out using CR2032-type coin cells with Li metal chips (MTI Corporation, 16 mm diameter, 0.6 mm thick) as the counter and reference electrodes. The oxidative stability of the electrolyte was evaluated by LSV scans from OCV to 4.5 V (versus Li⁺/Li) at a scan rate of 1 mV s⁻¹ against stainless steel (SS) discs and aluminum (Al) foil as the current collectors. For lithium plating/stripping tests, Li|Li symmetrical cells were cycled at different current densities of 0.5 mA cm⁻² and 1.0 mA cm⁻², respectively, with a polarization time of 1 h in each direction. In the case of the lithium plating/stripping rate capability study, current densities were varied from 0.2 to 1.0 mA cm⁻². Commercial LiFePO₄ cathode and graphite anode with the respective areal capacities of 2.0 and 2.4 mA h cm⁻² were obtained from CUSTOMCELLS and utilized to assemble graphite||LiFePO₄ full cells. For coin cells, the commercial electrodes were cut into circular discs with a diameter of 16 mm. A Celgard 2325 membrane (17 mm diameter, 25 μ m thick) was incorporated as the separator soaked with 120 μ L of the LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte in each coin cell. To fabricate graphite||LiFePO₄ pouch cells, the respective commercial electrodes were cut into rectangular shapes (5.6 cm × 4.3 cm). One piece of Celgard 2325 membrane (6 cm × 5 cm) was used as the separator. The quantity of the LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte in the pouch cells was limited to 3.7 μ L per milligram of LiFePO₄ (a total of 271.1 mg of active material in the electrode). After the electrolyte was injected into the pouch cells, they were subjected to an aging process at room temperature for 24 h. The C-rates and specific capacities of the graphite||LiFePO₄ full cells were calculated based on the theoretical capacity and corresponding mass loading of LiFePO₄. Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV), chronoamperometry, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) tests were performed on a Bio-Logic VMP3 potentiostat. Lithium plating/stripping tests and galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments were conducted using a Neware battery tester. All the electrochemical experiments were carried out at 25 °C.

The thermal shutdown characteristic of the LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolyte was evaluated and compared with that of the commercial LP30 electrolyte (1 M LiPF₆ in 1:1 v/v of EC/DMC) within a graphite||LiFePO₄ full-cell configuration using Swagelok cells. The cells containing each electrolyte were initially cycled at the current rate of 0.1C at room temperature (25 °C) to validate their electrochemical activities. The cells were subsequently cycled at the elevated temperatures of 80 °C and 120 °C, respectively. Before starting the cycling process, the cells were allowed to rest at the respective high temperatures for 1.5 h (including the time required to attend to a thermal equilibrium inside the cell). Moreover, to investigate the effect of Diels-Alder oligomers on the thermal stability of the PP/PE/PP separators and safety thresholds of the LIBs at elevated temperatures, the open circuit potentials of fully charged (at room temperature) graphite||LiFePO₄ Swagelok cells incorporating respective LP30 and LiTFSI_{0.15}DMFu_{0.8}VC_{1.0} electrolytes were monitored at 150 °C and 170 °C. The cells were charged at room temperature, heat-treated at 120 °C for 1.5 h, and then transferred to an oven at 150 °C or 170 °C. The open-circuit potentials of the cells at 150 °C or 170 °C were measured at 5-min intervals.

Post-Cycling Characterization: The surface morphologies and XPS characterization of cycled lithium anodes were examined after plating/stripping experiments by disassembling the coin cells and rinsing the cycled lithium electrodes with 1,2-dimethoxyethane solvent to remove residual electrolyte components. The electrodes were then dried overnight. All these procedures were performed in an argon-filled glove box. Finally, the lithium electrodes were transferred to the scanning electron microscope and X-ray photoelectron spectrometer using airtight transfer vessels.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

electrolyte formulation, lithium-ion batteries, safety, thermal runaway, thermal shutdown

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